

Deliverable 6.1

Global architecture for automatically built software tools catalogue

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List of Acronyms

ACID	Atomicity, Consistency, Isolation, Durability
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ASCL	Astrophysics Source Code Library
BSD	Berkeley Software Distribution
CCSD	Centre pour la Communication Scientifique Directe
CD	continuous deployment
CERN	Organisation Européenne pour la Recherche Nucléaire (European Organization for Nuclear Research)
CFF	Citation File Format
CHAOSS	Community Health Analytics Open Source Software
CI	continuous integration
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (National Centre for Scientific Research)
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DB	database
DCTERMS	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative Terms
DINUM	Direction interministérielle du Numérique
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPROD	Data Product Ontology
EMBL-EBI	European Molecular Biology Laboratory – European Bioinformatics Institute
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud

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FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reuse
GIL	Global Interpreter Lock
GPU	General Public License
HAL	Hyper Articles en Ligne
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
I/O	Input/Output
ID	Identifier
ISNI	International Standard Name Identifier
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
JSONB	JavaScript Object Notation Binary
LUMEN	Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network
MFO	Mathematisches Forschungsinstitut Oberwolfach
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MPA	Multi-Page Applications
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NASDAQ	National Association of Securities Dealers Automated Quotations
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
ODCS	Open Data Contract Standard
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OS	Operating System
OSSR	Open-source Scientific Software and Service Repository
PWA	Progressive Web App
PyPI	Python Package Index

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ReSA	Research Software Alliance
REST	Representational State Transfer
RNRS	Répertoire national des structures de recherche
ROR	Research Organisation Registry
RSD	Research Software Directory
SEO	search engine optimization
SILL	Socle Interministériel de Logiciels Libres
SPA	single-page application
SPDX	System Package Data Exchange
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSI	Software Sustainability Institute
SSPL	Server Side Public License
SWH	Software Heritage
SWHID	Software Heritage Identifier
UI	user interface
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
UX	user experience

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the global architecture for an automatically built research software catalogue within the LUMEN project (Work Package 6). It addresses a critical gap in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) ecosystem: the lack of a unified, multidisciplinary infrastructure for discovering, citing, and reusing research software across scientific domains.

Context and Objectives

Research software is a fundamental component of modern scientific workflows, yet remains significantly underrepresented in traditional research information systems. While publications and datasets benefit from established infrastructures and persistent identifiers, software often lacks proper documentation, citation mechanisms, and discovery tools. The LUMEN software catalogue aims to bridge this gap by providing a comprehensive, FAIR-compliant infrastructure that aggregates, enriches, and exposes research software metadata from multiple authoritative sources.

Key Contributions

Metadata Standardization: The catalogue adopts CodeMeta as its reference ontology, ensuring consistent software description across heterogeneous sources. This standardization enables interoperability with existing EOSC services and supports the implementation of FAIR principles for research software.

Multi-Source Aggregation Strategy: The architecture harvests metadata from code repositories (GitHub, GitLab), research archives (HAL, Zenodo), preservation services (Software Heritage), and domain-specific registries (bio.tools, swMATH). An entity matching mechanism identifies and consolidates duplicate entries, while enrichment processes add value through citation analysis, dependency tracking, and licence harmonization.

Data Mesh Implementation: The catalogue is designed as a Data Product within the LUMEN federation, demonstrating a concrete application of Data Mesh principles. It provides standardized APIs and formal data contracts following DPROD and ODCS standards, enabling seamless integration with WP4 (White Label Platform), WP3 (MetaSearch), and potentially external EOSC services.

Modular Architecture: The technical architecture comprises four main layers: data collection, entity resolution, metadata enrichment, and exploitation interfaces. This

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modularity ensures maintainability, scalability, and flexibility for future extensions to additional data sources or scientific domains.

Relevance for LUMEN and EOSC

Within LUMEN, the software catalogue serves as the authoritative source for software metadata, eliminating redundant harvesting efforts across Work Packages and demonstrating effective cross-WP collaboration. For the broader EOSC ecosystem, it contributes to closing the research output triangle by linking software with publications and datasets, supporting reproducibility, and promoting open science practices.

The catalogue's adherence to community standards (CodeMeta, SPDX¹ for licences) and persistent identifiers (DOI, SWHID, ORCID) ensures long-term sustainability and interoperability with existing EOSC infrastructure components, positioning it as a valuable resource for the European research community beyond the project's lifetime.

Next Steps

The implementation roadmap includes finalizing Data Product and Data Contract specifications by the end of 2026, developing production-grade APIs, implementing disciplinary classification mechanisms, and coordinating operational deployment with other LUMEN services.

1. Introduction and context

Research software plays a fundamental role in the production, dissemination and reuse of scientific knowledge. This awareness extends beyond traditional computer science domains to encompass virtually all academic disciplines, from the natural sciences and engineering to the social sciences and humanities. Research software has emerged as a scientific output of equal importance to publications and data, with these three facets of academic knowledge interacting closely with one another. However, software cannot simply be assimilated to publications or datasets.

¹ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q2297620>

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While considerable progress has been made in developing infrastructures and practices for publications and research data, software presents unique challenges that require specific approaches and solutions. It is a distinct research output with its own lifecycle, practices of development, and conditions of reuse. Despite its growing importance, the current infrastructures for discovery and access to research outputs often fail to take these specificities into account.

This situation is also evident within the *GoTriple*², a platform that aggregates research outputs in the field of social sciences and humanities. Although GoTriple provides valuable services for the discovery and connection of publications and data, its current handling of software still follows the same logic applied to textual outputs. For instance, software records are treated as if they were standard research publications, resulting in significant limitations:

- no information on software licensing,
- no links to the actual code repositories,
- absence of software-specific metadata such as programming language, dependencies, or versioning.

As an example, software entries deposited in HAL³, France's national open-access archive, and then displayed in GoTriple (see example record⁴) illustrate these shortcomings. The resulting records are incomplete and do not support proper understanding, citation, or reuse of the software.

To address these challenges, it is essential to design **a more specific and pertinent approach for software** within the research ecosystem. This includes the ability to enrich metadata directly from source code repositories, to capture software-specific descriptors, and to ensure automatic processing without relying on manual interventions from researchers [1].

Developing such dedicated workflows is crucial, not only to improve the visibility and traceability of research software, but also to recognize its value as a first-class research output, fully integrated alongside publications and data.

2. State of the art and existing tools

The landscape of research software cataloging is not one that requires creation from scratch. Rather, substantial infrastructure already exists that can be leveraged and extended. Software catalogue tools have been developed and deployed by various

² <http://www.gotriple.eu> & <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q126085000>

³ <https://about.hal.science/en/> & <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q3144107>

⁴ <https://www.gotriple.eu/documents/ftinraparis%3Aoa%3AHAL%3Ahal-02796286v1>

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institutions and communities worldwide to improve the **visibility and discoverability** of research software, for instance:

- Astrophysics Source Code Library (ASCL) – a community-driven repository listing astrophysics software described in scientific publications, providing stable references and links to source code.
- swMATH⁵ – a registry for mathematical software, which links code to scholarly publications using metadata harvested from zbMATH Open.
- Bio.tools⁶ [13] is a community-driven, open-access registry that provides detailed information about bioinformatics software, databases, workflows, and services, supported by ELIXIR Europe.
- NASA Software Catalog⁷ – focuses on the dissemination of NASA-developed software, offering descriptive metadata, licensing information, and download links.
- code.gouv.fr⁸ – the French public sector’s open catalogue for government-developed software, promoting reuse and transparency of publicly funded code.
- Research Software Directory (RSD)⁹ – developed by the Netherlands eScience Center, this platform enhances the visibility and reuse of research software by presenting it in its research context, including associated publications, developers, and social activity.
- ESCAPE Open-source Scientific Software and Service Repository (OSSR)¹⁰ – a sustainable open-access repository for sharing scientific software, services, and datasets in astro-particle-physics, built as a curated Zenodo community to support the full software lifecycle.

Crucially, metadata schemes for software have also been developed and are seeing adoption. **CodeMeta**¹¹ stands out as a particularly important standard - a JSON-LD format for software metadata that serves as a crosswalk between 25+ different metadata vocabularies. CodeMeta extends Schema.org¹²'s vocabulary to meet academic needs while ensuring machine-readability and interoperability. This makes **CodeMeta** particularly well-suited for building rich, standardized software catalogues.

⁵ <https://zbmath.org/software/> & <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q20827380>

⁶ <https://bio.tools/t> & <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q111239108>

⁷ <https://software.nasa.gov/>

⁸ <https://code.gouv.fr/fr/> & <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q115329121>

⁹ <https://research-software-directory.org/page/about> &

¹⁰ <https://escape-ossr.gitlab.io/ossr-pages/> & <http://doi.org/10.17616/R31NJN5V>

¹¹ <https://codemeta.github.io/>

¹² <https://schema.org/> & <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q3475322>

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Complementing this, the **Citation File Format**¹³ (**CFF**) [7, 8] has gained widespread adoption, especially through platforms like GitHub¹⁴. While **CFF** focuses specifically on standardizing how software should be cited—rather than describing its technical or functional attributes—it plays a vital role in ensuring proper attribution and recognition for developers.

Together, **CodeMeta** and **CFF** address distinct but equally important aspects of software metadata: **CodeMeta** for detailed software description and **CFF** for citation guidance. Both standards are increasingly used in tandem, providing a robust foundation for automated metadata exchange, processing, and the broader adoption of research software catalogues [3].

The strategic approach is therefore not to reinvent these wheels, but to build upon existing infrastructure, standards, and best practices while addressing specific needs and gaps in the current ecosystem.

France has developed a national software catalogue initiative through its Committee for Open Science¹⁵, building upon two complementary infrastructures: **Software Heritage**¹⁶ (for universal archiving and persistent identifiers) and *HAL* (the national open archive). The French open source software catalogue¹⁷ operates by harvesting software metadata from *HAL*, which has been extended to support *CodeMeta*-based software descriptions.

This implementation demonstrates key principles that our project will follow:

- **Leveraging existing infrastructures** rather than duplicating them;
- **Prioritizing automation and interoperability**;
- **Reducing researcher workload** by sourcing metadata directly from repositories;
- **Maintaining metadata quality** through structured and repository-based sources.

The French catalogue exemplifies how modern research software infrastructure should function: as an integrated ecosystem rather than isolated components. Software Heritage provides archiving and persistent identification; HAL provides scholarly communication infrastructure and metadata management; the extension to

¹³ <https://citation-file-format.github.io/> & <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q108218387>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/> & <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q364>

¹⁵ <https://www.ovvirlascience.fr/the-committee-for-open-science/>

¹⁶ <https://www.softwareheritage.org/software-heritage-faq/> & <https://ror.org/02etvq888>

¹⁷ <https://logiciels.catalogue-esr.fr/>

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support CodeMeta provides interoperability; and automated tools reduce the burden on researchers while maintaining quality.

This approach acknowledges that software catalogues exist, standards exist, and tools exist - the challenge is not creation but integration, automation, and adoption.

Beyond national efforts like France's integrated approach, several international initiatives are actively fostering the discoverability, interoperability, and sustainability of research software. The **SciCodes Consortium**¹⁸ stands out as a collaborative network of scientific software registries and repositories. *SciCodes* promotes best practices, metadata standardization (notably through *CodeMeta* and *CFF*), and cross-disciplinary search capabilities, enabling researchers to find and reuse software regardless of its origin. Similarly, **Research Software Alliance**¹⁹ (ReSA) and **FORCE11 Software Citation Working Group**²⁰ drive global adoption of software citation standards and metadata schemas, ensuring software is recognized as a first-class research output. The **Software Sustainability Institute**²¹ (SSI) and **ELIXIR**²² **Tools Platform** provides frameworks and training for sustainable software development and metadata management, further bridging gaps between domains. These initiatives collectively demonstrate a shift towards an integrated, standards-based ecosystem—prioritizing automation, interoperability, and the reduction of researcher burden, while ensuring software is discoverable, citable, and preserved for the long term.

Ensuring Metadata Quality: The Repository as Primary Source

A fundamental insight for ensuring metadata quality is that **the authoritative source of information about software resides in its code repository**. This principle has several important implications:

1. Intrinsic metadata: Authors are best positioned to describe their software and should provide metadata directly within their code repositories. This is typically accomplished through a `codemeta.json` file at the root of the repository.
2. Version control integration: Because metadata resides in the version-controlled repository, it evolves with the software itself, maintaining accurate descriptions across versions.

¹⁸ <https://scicodes.net/>

¹⁹ <https://ror.org/007tfm130>

²⁰ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q33049686>

²¹ <https://ror.org/0455awd29>

²² <https://ror.org/044rwnt51>

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3. Automated extraction: Modern tools (e.g., GROBID²³) can automatically extract metadata from repositories, reducing manual curation overhead and ensuring freshness of information.

Linking Publications, data and Software: Closing the Loop

A critical aspect of integrating software into the research ecosystem is establishing links between software, publications and data [18, 19]. This connection serves multiple purposes:

- Enabling reproducibility by identifying the exact software versions used in published research
- Providing credit to software developers through citation
- Improving software discoverability through publication databases

The software catalogue task in the LUMEN project²⁴ aims to extend and enhance this foundation, developing recommendations for European-scale software catalogue integration that leverage existing infrastructures while ensuring interoperability, quality, and sustainability. Our work recognizes software as a distinct research output requiring specialized approaches, while maintaining seamless integration with publication and data ecosystems.

3. Methodology for this report

Developing a comprehensive research software catalogue required a balanced approach combining research, collaboration, and practical experimentation. Our methodology comprised four key phases:

Exploration of Existing Resources

We began with an extensive review of existing research software catalogues and repositories, both academic and non-academic. This allows us to identify common data types, effective interface designs, and best practices in data organization and accessibility. Ultimately, this analysis informed the structural and functional design of our catalogue. Below is a list of additional websites and catalogues, supplementary to those previously mentioned, that were examined during this phase:

²³ <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/swh:1:dir:8198c5c2aa4baff65f05edac696b550d222e7ecc>

²⁴ <https://lumenproject.eu/about/>

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- [Framalibre](https://framalibre.org/)²⁵: A French directory promoting free and open-source software alternatives to proprietary solutions, curated by the non-profit Framasoft²⁶.
- [OpenHub](https://openhub.net/explore/projects)²⁷: A comprehensive directory and analytics platform for open-source projects, offering insights into code activity, contributors, and project health.
- [AlternativeTo](https://alternativeto.net/)²⁸: A user-driven platform that suggests and compares software alternatives, helping users find similar tools to those they already know.
- [Research Software Directory](https://research-software-directory.org/software)²⁹: A curated registry of research software tools and projects, designed to improve discoverability and reuse in academic and scientific communities.

Engagement with the Research Community

We conducted targeted discussions with researchers to understand their specific needs, challenges, and expectations regarding research software discovery and reuse. These insights provided refined perspectives on what features would be most valuable in a software catalogue, as well as the types of metadata and documentation that researchers prioritise when evaluating software for their work.

Practical Experimentation and Proof of Concept

To validate our ideas and assumptions, we built a proof-of-concept (POC) using the open-source **Socle Interministériel de Logiciels Libres (SILL)**³⁰ platform, developed by **Direction interministérielle du Numérique (DINUM)**³¹ [14]. This hands-on approach allowed us to identify potential technical and operational challenges early in the process, ensuring that our solutions are both robust and scalable.

Collaboration with Data and Indexing Experts

Consultations with experts in scientific data management and indexing further refined our approach to metadata standards, interoperability, and data integration. We also partnered with organizations like *Software Heritage*, which are actively engaged in similar efforts to gather and preserve code. Their input ensured the software catalogue structure supports effective search and categorization.

²⁵ <https://framalibre.org/> & <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q30213882>

²⁶ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q3080414>

²⁷ <https://openhub.net/explore/projects> & <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q124688>

²⁸ <https://alternativeto.net/> & <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q3613175>

²⁹ <https://research-software-directory.org/software>

³⁰ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q56320927>

³¹ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q72587257>

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By integrating exploration, community engagement, experimentation, and expert collaboration, we have established a strong foundation for a research software catalogue that effectively meets current demands and remains adaptable to future developments in the research software landscape.

4. Laying the foundation: Standardising Software Metadata

Before proceeding with software architecture and implementation, it is essential to establish a clear conceptual framework. The initial phase focuses on defining the core data elements and representative use cases that will inform the design, structure, and technological choices for developing the research software catalogue.

The first critical step is to address the challenge of software metadata [9, 10]. Since we aim to aggregate data from diverse, existing sources, we immediately encounter a key obstacle: each source uses its own schema, sometimes using software metadata ontology, often not. To create a cohesive, high-quality dataset, we must select a robust ontology that aligns with our goals and can serve as a common framework then identify or develop crosswalks to map each source's schema to our chosen ontology, ensuring consistency and interoperability.

Given our commitment to prioritizing metadata quality and automation, we must also determine which metadata fields are essential and must be present in each source. In this section, we will:

- Evaluate and select an **ontology** that best fits our requirements to describe **software metadata**
- Identify **computed metadata** that enhance value for end users.
- Determine **metadata** utility across various **use cases**, including the ability to discover, evaluate, and utilise software effectively.
- Conduct a comprehensive analysis of our **data sources** to ascertain the information they provide, their **reliability**, and the schemas they employ.
- Review **scientific identifiers** to identify resources that facilitate the disambiguation of data.

By addressing these steps, we will establish a solid foundation for a unified, user-centric metadata framework.

4.1 Selection of the software metadata ontology

Schema.org is defined within the sources as a comprehensive collection of vocabularies for structured data use on the internet and beyond, functioning primarily as a linked data schema that is frequently employed by search engines to improve findability. Specifically concerning software, *Schema.org* provides several foundational classes for describing these digital assets, notably, SoftwareSourceCode³², and SoftwareApplication³³. *Schema.org* could be enough to describe a software but there is a requirement for an extension of this ontology to fit more the needs of research.

The *CodeMeta* ontology [6] is a specialized metadata standard designed to describe software projects in a structured, machine-readable way, with a strong emphasis on supporting discoverability, citation, and reuse in research and scientific contexts. Built as an extension of the widely used *Schema.org* vocabulary, *CodeMeta* provides a comprehensive set of properties tailored specifically for software, including details such as code repository location, programming language, version, licence, dependencies, and documentation. This ontology is particularly valuable for academic and research software, as it enables consistent and rich metadata representation across repositories, journals, and data archives. By facilitating interoperability and compliance with FAIR³⁴ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, CodeMeta helps researchers and developers properly credit, share, and integrate software into scholarly workflows. Its adoption by major platforms and publishers underscores its role as a key standard for software metadata in the research community.

The Dublin Core Metadata Initiative Terms³⁵ (DCTERMS) is a standardized, extensible set of properties designed to describe a wide range of resources, including software, in a simple yet interoperable way. While DCTERMS itself is not specifically tailored for software, its flexible vocabulary—such as terms like `dct:title`, `dct:creator`, `dct:description`, `dct:date`, `dct:license`, and `dct:hasVersion`—can be effectively applied to document software metadata. These terms allow for the capture of essential information about software projects, such as authorship, versioning, licensing, and functional descriptions. However, DCTERMS lacks specialized properties for software-specific attributes (e.g., programming language, dependencies, or repository location), so it is often used in conjunction with more domain-specific ontologies like CodeMeta or DataCite³⁶ for

³² <https://schema.org/SoftwareSourceCode>

³³ <https://schema.org/SoftwareApplication>

³⁴ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q29032644>

³⁵ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q108771890>

³⁶ <https://ror.org/04wxnsj81>

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comprehensive software documentation. Its broad adoption and compatibility with linked data principles make DCTERMS a useful foundation for general software metadata, particularly in digital libraries, repositories, and cross-disciplinary research contexts.

The DataCite Metadata Schema³⁷ is a widely adopted standard primarily designed for citing and describing research datasets, but it also plays a significant role in documenting research software. While not exclusively focused on software, DataCite provides a robust framework for assigning persistent identifiers (such as DOIs³⁸) and capturing essential metadata about software projects, including title, creators, version, publication date, licence, and related documentation. This enables software to be cited, discovered, and reused in a manner analogous to traditional research outputs. DataCite's emphasis on persistent identification and interoperability makes it particularly valuable for integrating software into the scholarly record, supporting reproducibility, and ensuring proper attribution. Many software repositories and academic publishers now use DataCite metadata to enhance the visibility and impact of research software within the broader research ecosystem.

Based on the analysis of the ontologies presented above, we recommend adopting **CodeMeta** as the most suitable strategy for documenting software metadata within this project. CodeMeta stands out due to its specialized design for software, offering a comprehensive and well-defined set of properties tailored to the unique requirements of software projects—such as code repositories, dependencies, and licensing. As an extension of the widely used Schema.org vocabulary, it ensures broad compatibility and ease of integration with existing systems. Furthermore, CodeMeta's alignment with FAIR principles and its established crosswalks³⁹ to other standards (e.g., DataCite, DCTERMS) enhance interoperability and simplify adoption. Its growing implementation in research tools and platforms, such as Bolognese⁴⁰ and CodeMetaGenerator⁴¹, further supports its role as a future-proof and practical choice for the research community.

You can explore in detail the software metadata in the [annexe](#).

4.2 Metadata and related data that matters

When users search for software packages, they often seek more than just raw metadata; they also value aggregated or computed data that provides deeper

³⁷ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q105762834>

³⁸ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q25670>

³⁹ <https://codemeta.github.io/crosswalk/>

⁴⁰ <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/swh:1:dir:412d864db529639b2cbe374f0f5eeb37de1f0946>

⁴¹ <https://archive.softwareheritage.org/swh:1:dir:1f81ab46983dedb7baa504c14be33101b6e98117>

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insights into the software's capabilities, quality, and suitability for their needs. While many of these data points do not fit within the traditional metadata fields, their inclusion in a software catalogue can significantly enhance the user experience. This section explores several types of computed metadata that add substantial value for users, enabling them to more effectively discover, evaluate, utilise and cite software packages [4, 5].

Functional Classification and Keywords

The software category or associated keywords can serve as a powerful indicator of a package's features and intended use. Rather than relying on generic tags, a dedicated field with a well-defined ontology can precisely describe what the software does. This level of detail helps users quickly identify software that matches their requirements, reducing the time spent sifting through irrelevant options.

Indicators factor of **code quality**: Software quality becomes a trend topic because it gives a vibe on how reusable or easy to modify a software package is. It could help the user when searching for a software to get an indicator of code quality. We already notice that the European Project named Everse⁴² and Community Health Analytics Open Source Software⁴³ (CHAOSS) already worked on that topic. We could use their work to improve the software pages of our project.

Security audit or report of the software package: This is not common on most of the research software packages but we think it's interesting to mention that, especially when researchers work with sensitive data. It could help the searcher in their research to quickly see the indicator on how much tested and safe it is to use a software based on a security report.

A lot of research software is about data processing. An important matter then is the **input data format**, or supported data type. If you find a software that doesn't support the data you want to process, it becomes useless.

The **citation** and **relatedWork** fields in CodeMeta are designed to link software to scholarly works—such as articles, websites, or technical reports—providing a structured way to document and credit the scientific context of software. However, in practice, these fields are often underutilized or incomplete. Not many code repositories include any citation information, and many scientists lack the time, tools, or awareness to maintain comprehensive CodeMeta files. While initiatives like CODEMETASOFT⁴⁴ aim to automate and simplify metadata creation, the current

⁴² <https://everse.software/about/objectives/>

⁴³ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q50866814>

⁴⁴ <https://oscars-project.eu/projects/codemetasoft>

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fragmented and manual approach limits the reliability of these fields for tracking software-related creative works.

There are models of impact quotes that define the importance of an article among the publications. We could also use a model here to get a more accurate impact of the citation than just a number of quotes.

All these computed metadata are not specially mentioned in *CodeMeta*, but they can easily be added using *Schema.org* ontology. We could also propose some additions to the next CodeMeta version to fit a more detailed description of a software.

4.3 Defining Essential Metadata for Discovery and Use

We collect extensive metadata to define and describe software, but not all of it is equally valuable to users. While it's tempting to showcase the breadth of our data harvesting, presenting everything at once can overwhelm users, making it harder for them to find and understand the information that matters most. Instead, we should prioritise clarity and relevance: start by surfacing only the most important metadata, then offer users the option to explore deeper if needed. To determine what's most relevant, we analyzed four key use cases:

- **Software discovering:** what makes it easy to discover a software package ?
- **Evaluating ease of trial:** what information does a user need to evaluate if they can easily test a software
- **Assessing daily usability:** what information a user need to evaluate if they can use a software package in daily use
- **Understanding modifiability**—how easily users can adapt or extend the software

By focusing on these scenarios, we ensure users see what's most important first, with the flexibility to dive deeper when necessary.

Discoverability: Is it related to what I am looking for ?

When researchers search for software, they typically use keywords related to the research field and required functionalities. The result then shows overview of each software entry, including:

- **Name:** The official or commonly used name identifying the software.
- **Description:** A brief summary of the software's main features and purpose.
- **Tags:** A set of keywords describing the software's domain, key features, and data types.

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- **Mentions-related documents:** related documents give more in depth details on software package
- **Citations:** The number of citations and the origin and type of the citation help to situate a software package in a field or ecosystem

Ease of trial: Can I try it ?

Once relevant software is identified, researchers need to determine whether they can install and run it. The following information is typically required:

- **Software Dependencies:** Additional software or libraries required for installation and execution.
- **Quickstart documentation:** A quick start documentation that guide the user to run the software package
- **Programming Languages Used:** To assess alignment with the researcher's technical expertise when software binaries are not available and the user has to compile them manually.
- **Binary availability:** is there a link to download the software binary or does the user have to compile it.
- **Platform Compatibility:** Supported operating systems and environments.
- **Hardware Requirements:** Minimum and recommended hardware specifications.
- **Sample Data Availability:** Access to sample datasets for testing and reproducing published results.
- **Data Format Compatibility:** Supported input and output data formats to ensure interoperability with users' own datasets.
- **Licence:** The software licence terms must be reviewed to ensure that the developers allow trials

Usability: Can I adopt it in my workflow ?

For researchers considering the adoption of a software package in a production environment, several factors must be carefully evaluated to ensure its suitability and reliability. The software entry should include:

- Documentation
 - Usability: Comprehensive and clear documentation is vital. It should detail all available settings and configurations, enabling users to achieve optimal performance and avoid potential pitfalls.
 - Methodological Transparency: The software's underlying methodology, algorithms, and data processing techniques should be thoroughly

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documented. This transparency allows users to understand the approach taken by the developers and to assess its appropriateness for their specific needs.

- **Licence:** The software’s licence terms must be reviewed to ensure compliance with the intended use, especially in commercial or institutional contexts.
- **Sustainability and Support:** Consider the long-term viability of the software. Is there ongoing funding or institutional support? A robust and active community can also be a strong indicator of the software’s sustainability, providing resources for troubleshooting, updates, and collaborative development.

Software extensibility: Can I modify and extend it ?

In research contexts, it is often necessary to modify or extend existing software. The following are key points for users to assess the feasibility of such modifications:

- **Licence Permissions:** Clarification of legal rights to modify, redistribute, or publish the software.
- **Programming Languages Used:** To assess alignment with the researcher’s technical expertise, as each software is often written in one or more programming languages.
- **Documentation:** Availability of technical documentation or architectural overviews of the software to facilitate understanding and modification of the code.

As demonstrated through the various use cases above, a substantial amount of data must be collected to provide users with a comprehensive view within the catalogue. However, this process presents significant challenges, as the required information cannot be obtained from a single source, and data formats vary considerably across different endpoints. The following section provides a detailed review of the potential data sources from which relevant information can be extracted.

Summary of interesting information according to use case

This section outlines the fields to be presented to users, tailored to their specific use cases for engaging with the software catalogue.

This analysis will inform the subsequent design of the user interface, ensuring alignment with user needs and workflows.

	Discoverability	Trial	Use	Modify
--	-----------------	-------	-----	--------

Name	Useful	No	No	No
Description	Useful	No	No	No
Tags & keywords	Useful	No	No	No
Software Dependencies	No	Useful	Useful	Useful
Documentation	Useful	Useful	Useful	Useful
Binary availability	No	Useful	Useful	No
Platform Compatibility	No	Useful	Useful	Useful
Hardware Requirements	No	Useful	Useful	No
Sample Data Availability	No	Useful	Useful	No
Data Format Compatibility	No	Useful	Useful	No
Licence	No	Useful	Useful	Useful
Programming Language	No	Useful	Useful	Useful
Community	No	No	Useful	Useful
Funding	No	No	Useful	No

4.4 Sources analysis

We've established a framework for describing software metadata and identified which data points are most valuable for researchers in various use cases. Our initial approach assumed an ideal scenario—one where all relevant metadata are readily available to users. But how often does this ideal align with reality?

To answer this, we need to analyze what information is actually provided by existing software metadata sources. We reached out to research communities to learn where and how they publish and store their software information. While the responses we received are not exhaustive, they offer a valuable starting point for understanding current practices in software metadata management.

In our analysis, we prioritised sources that provide APIs for automated data retrieval. At this stage of the project, we've chosen not to rely on web scraping for metadata extraction. Instead, we focus on sources that support proper API-based data export, ensuring reliability and scalability for our needs.

Non exhaustive list of source

HAL

HAL (Hyper Articles en Ligne) is an open archive platform for scientific research. It allows researchers to deposit, share, and access scholarly articles, preprints, theses, and other academic publications. HAL is interdisciplinary, covering all fields of research, and is a key player in the open science movement, promoting free and immediate access to scientific knowledge [21].

HAL was launched in 2001 by the **Centre pour la Communication Scientifique Directe**⁴⁵ (CCSD), a unit of the French National Centre for Scientific Research⁴⁶ (CNRS). It is a non-profit, publicly funded platform.

HAL is committed to the principle that scientific research should be freely accessible to all, without paywalls or restrictions. HAL ensures the permanent archiving and accessibility of deposited works. It helps researchers comply with open access mandates from funding agencies and institutions. HAL is integrated with French and European research ecosystems, supporting both individual researchers and institutions.

HAL is the largest open archive for French research and one of the most important in Europe. It is widely used by French universities, research labs, and funding bodies. It also interoperates with international repositories and platforms like arXiv⁴⁷, PubMed Central⁴⁸, and OpenAIRE⁴⁹.

HAL provides metadata in the CodeMeta format, though some records may lack in standard identifiers, particularly for authors (no ORCID⁵⁰). The platform employs a moderated submission process to maintain data quality. While HAL currently hosts relatively few software packages (a bit more than a thousand), the available data are robust and reliable [20].

Zenodo

Zenodo⁵¹ is a general-purpose, open-access repository developed to enable researchers to share, preserve, and make all types of research outputs publicly available. It supports datasets, software, publications, presentations, images, and

⁴⁵ <https://www.ccsd.cnrs.fr/en/ccsd-the-unit/> & <https://ror.org/00680hx61>

⁴⁶ <https://www.cnrs.fr/en/le-cnrs/missions> & <https://ror.org/02feahw73>

⁴⁷ <https://arxiv.org/> & <https://ror.org/00m2zh467>

⁴⁸ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q229883>

⁴⁹ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q25106053>

⁵⁰ See in the next part on research identifiers 4.5

⁵¹ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q22661177>

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other research artifacts. Zenodo is widely used across all scientific disciplines and is known for its flexibility and integration with other research tools.

Zenodo was launched in 2013 and is still run by CERN⁵² (the European Organization for Nuclear Research) and *OpenAIRE*, a European initiative promoting open access to research. It is a non-profit, publicly funded platform.

Zenodo is committed to making research outputs freely available to everyone, supporting the principles of open science. It assigns a Digital Object Identifier (*DOI*) to each deposit, ensuring citability and long-term accessibility. It integrates with *GitHub*, *Figshare*⁵³, and other platforms, making it easy to archive software, datasets, and other digital research products. Zenodo helps researchers comply with open access and data sharing mandates from funders and institutions, including those from the European Commission⁵⁴.

Zenodo is used by researchers worldwide and is especially popular in Europe due to its *OpenAIRE* affiliation. As of 2025, Zenodo hosts millions of records and is a go-to platform for researchers needing a quick, reliable, and free way to share and archive their work.

Zenodo stands out as a major hub for collecting metadata about software packages. Its API currently indexes over 300,000 entries identified as software. However, a preliminary analysis reveals significant variability in data quality. Some records do not even represent actual software packages, while others range from well-documented entries to those with minimal or missing metadata.

The platform's data model for software packages aligns closely with our own, and Zenodo supports CodeMeta export, which is promising for interoperability. The main challenge lies in effectively filtering the database to identify genuine software packages with reliable and comprehensive metadata. Addressing this issue will be key to leveraging Zenodo's extensive repository for our needs.

Biotoools

bio.tools is a community-driven registry and discovery platform for bioinformatics tools, software, and databases. It provides a centralized, searchable catalogue of bioinformatics resources, including detailed metadata, documentation, and links to help researchers and developers find, compare, and use tools for biological data analysis.

⁵² <https://ror.org/01ggx4157>

⁵³ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q17013516>

⁵⁴ <https://ror.org/00k4n6c32>

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bio.tools was launched in 2013 as part of the *ELIXIR* infrastructure, a European intergovernmental organization that supports life-science data resources and bioinformatics tools. It's still maintained by *ELIXIR*, specifically by the *ELIXIR* Tools Platform. It is a non-profit, publicly funded initiative supported by *ELIXIR*'s member states and nodes across Europe.

bio.tools aims to be the most complete and up-to-date registry of bioinformatics tools and databases. The platform encourages contributions from tool developers and users, ensuring broad coverage and accuracy. It uses a standardized schema (based on the **EDAM**⁵⁵ ontology [15]) to describe tools, making it easier to search, compare, and integrate them. All information in *bio.tools* is freely accessible, supporting open science and reproducibility in bioinformatics. *bio.tools* is integrated with other **ELIXIR services** and international bioinformatics resources, facilitating interoperability and workflow development [16].

bio.tools is the go-to platform for discovering bioinformatics tools, with thousands of entries and a strong reputation in the life sciences community. While rooted in *ELIXIR*'s European infrastructure, bio.tools is used globally by researchers, developers, and educators. It complements general-purpose repositories (like *GitHub* or *Zenodo*) and specialized databases (like NCBI⁵⁶ or EMBL-EBI⁵⁷) by providing a curated, searchable index of tools.

bio.tools offers high-quality metadata for software packages through a well-designed API. However, the challenge lies in the fact that bio.tools employs its own schema for software description, necessitating the development of a crosswalk to effectively import data from their API. Fortunately, their comprehensive and detailed documentation proves to be highly valuable in this process.

swMath

The swMATH portal is a specialised information service for mathematical software. It serves as a comprehensive database and search engine for software in mathematics (e.g., numerical algorithms, symbolic computation tools, mathematical libraries), providing metadata, publication references and links to software sources to help researchers and practitioners discover and reuse mathematical software.

⁵⁵ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q117356000>

⁵⁶ <https://ror.org/02meqm098>

⁵⁷ <https://ror.org/02catss52>

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Historically, swMATH was initiated as a joint 2011–2013 project of **FIZ Karlsruhe**⁵⁸ and **Mathematisches Forschungsinstitut Oberwolfach**⁵⁹ (MFO) supported by the Leibniz Association⁶⁰, with the goal of providing a freely accessible resource for mathematical software [19]. Its development continues in collaboration with the Zuse Institute Berlin within the framework of the Forschungscampus Modal⁶¹. In 2022, swMATH data were incorporated into the zbMATH Open service, further connecting software entries with the broader mathematical literature.

swMATH is tailored specifically for mathematical software, filling a niche not covered by general-purpose software repositories. It provides detailed metadata, including descriptions, references, and links to source code or documentation. swMATH is integrated with zbMATH, allowing users to connect software with related mathematical literature and research. The platform promotes open access to mathematical software, supporting reproducibility and collaboration in mathematical research. It encourages contributions and feedback from the mathematical community to keep the database up-to-date and relevant.

swMATH is among the leading platforms for discovering mathematical software, with few direct competitors (e.g., MathRepo, Netlib.org) offering the same depth of coverage. It is widely used by mathematicians, computational scientists, and researchers who need to find, cite, or reuse mathematical software.

While swMATH boasts a meticulously curated database with extensive software coverage, its API does not currently support the standard CodeMeta format (an initiative for crosswalk mapping does exist, coordinated by FAIRCORE4EOSC project [31]) and some data fields may be incomplete, e.g., licence information, versioning, hardware/software requirements. Also, its scope is focussed on mathematical software (including some related benchmarks and services) rather than all research software. Nevertheless, the platform delivers prime-quality data, offering a wealth of detailed and reliable information within its domain.

GitHub

GitHub is a web-based platform used for version control and collaboration, allowing developers to work together on projects from anywhere. It hosts code repositories, tracks changes, and enables features like pull requests, issue tracking, and project management. A lot of researchers put their source code on it.

⁵⁸ <https://ror.org/0387prb75>

⁵⁹ <https://ror.org/001zbj766>

⁶⁰ <https://ror.org/01n6r0e97>

⁶¹ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q77436292>

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GitHub was launched in April 2008 by Tom Preston-Werner⁶², Chris Wanstrath⁶³, Scott Chacon⁶⁴ and PJ Hyett⁶⁵. GitHub was acquired by Microsoft⁶⁶ in June 2018 for \$7.5 billion and operates as a subsidiary.

GitHub's mission is to accelerate software development by making it easier for individuals and teams to build, ship, and maintain software. It emphasizes open-source collaboration, transparency, and community-driven development.

GitHub is the world's largest and most widely used platform for hosting and collaborating on software projects, with over 100 million users and millions of repositories as of 2025. It is a central hub for both open-source and private software development. In the research area, we can see that many research code is hosted on this platform.

While GitHub does not provide comprehensive software metadata (such as research categories or author affiliations) it offers the most current and detailed information about the code itself, including versions, development status, and activity. This makes GitHub an invaluable complementary source for software metadata, especially when paired with a main research entry.

GitLab

GitLab⁶⁷ is a web-based platform that provides a *Git*⁶⁸ repository manager, along with features for issue tracking, continuous integration/continuous deployment (CI/CD), and more. It enables teams to collaborate on software development, from planning and coding to testing, deployment, and monitoring—all in a single application.

GitLab was first released in 2011 by Ukrainian developers Dmitry Zaporozhets⁶⁹ and Sytse Sijbrandij⁷⁰. GitLab Inc. is a publicly traded company, listed on the NASDAQ stock exchange under the ticker "GTLB" since October 2021. It is not owned by a single entity but by its shareholders.

GitLab's mission is to enable everyone to contribute to software development, emphasizing transparency, collaboration, and automation. The platform is built on open-source principles, with both a free, open-core version and a commercial

⁶² <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q16602077>

⁶³ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q27940879>

⁶⁴ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q124519214>

⁶⁵ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q55760767>

⁶⁶ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q2283>

⁶⁷ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q16639197>

⁶⁸ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q186055>

⁶⁹ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q73463100>

⁷⁰ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q73462638>

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enterprise offering. *GitLab* promotes a “remote-first” culture and aims to make the entire DevOps lifecycle accessible and efficient for teams of all sizes.

It is used by research communities for its robust CI/CD capabilities, self-hosting options, and strong focus on security and compliance. More and more universities or research laboratories host their own *GitLab* instance to ensure the source code platform reliability and ownership.

Similar to GitHub in terms of the metadata it provides, *GitLab* instances can offer the most current and detailed information regarding the code itself, including version history, development status, and activity metrics. However, *GitLab* lacks specific research-oriented metadata. One notable challenge is that certain repositories may be protected, requiring user authentication on the platform to access the relevant URLs.

Software Heritage

Software Heritage is the largest public archive of software source code, often described as the "Library of Alexandria" for software [11]. It collects, preserves, and makes accessible the source code of all publicly available software, ensuring that this cultural and technical heritage is not lost over time. The platform provides unique identifiers for software artifacts, enabling precise referencing and long-term preservation.

Software Heritage was launched in 2016 by Roberto Di Cosmo⁷¹ and Stefano Zacchiroli⁷², both computer scientists. *Software Heritage* is run as a non-profit initiative hosted by Inria⁷³ (the French National Institute for Research in Digital Science and Technology), with support from UNESCO⁷⁴, the *European Commission*, and other public and private partners.

The mission of *Software Heritage* is to build a universal, permanent archive of all publicly available software, ensuring that future generations can access, study, and reuse the world’s software heritage. The platform emphasizes openness, transparency, and the preservation of digital knowledge for the benefit of researchers, developers, and society as a whole.

Software Heritage is unique in its focus on long-term archival and does not compete directly with commercial platforms like *GitHub* or *GitLab*. Instead, it complements them by providing a permanent, neutral archive of software artifacts. It is widely

⁷¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7493-5349>

⁷² <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4576-136X>

⁷³ <https://ror.org/02kvxyf05>

⁷⁴ <https://ror.org/04h4z8k05>

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recognized and used by academic institutions, open-source communities, and organizations concerned with digital preservation and software provenance.

The *Software Heritage archive*⁷⁵ primarily contains source code, with limited information regarding issues and software metadata. While this resource is notable for its resilience, it currently lacks certain valuable data. Nevertheless, it could serve as a unique identifier to disambiguate between two software artifacts, ensuring their identity.

Comparative analysis of reliability

In assessing the reliability and comprehensiveness of software metadata sources, it is essential to evaluate key attributes such as moderation practices, the extent of field coverage of CodeMeta schema, and the availability of *live* code-specific metadata.

Catalogue	Moderated	Field coverage	Code Metadata
Zenodo	No	Variable	Partial
SwMath	Yes	Good	Partial
bio.tools	Yes	Good	Partial
HAL	Yes	Good	Partial
Software Heritage	No	Partial	Partial
GitLab	Depends	Good	Yes
GitHub	No	Good	Yes

The exploration of various software metadata sources reveals that each platform offers unique strengths, making them collectively valuable for constructing a robust research software catalogue. While some sources, such as *Zenodo*, *SwMath*, *bio.tools*, and *HAL*, are closely tied to the research ecosystem—providing rich contextual information like project descriptions, links to academic publications, and disciplinary metadata—others, including *Software Heritage*, *GitLab*, and *GitHub*, excel in delivering up-to-date, live data on code development and versioning. This diversity ensures that a catalogue built from these sources can capture both the technical and scholarly dimensions of research software.

⁷⁵ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q112594892>

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It is important to distinguish between primary and secondary sources within this landscape. Primary sources, such as research data repositories (e.g., *Zenodo*), often contain original research outputs and associated software artifacts, while secondary sources (e.g., *GitHub*, *GitLab*) focus more on code metadata, version control, and collaborative development. However, the inclusion of *Zenodo* in a catalogue requires caution, as its lack of systematic moderation may result in variable metadata quality, potentially compromising the reliability of the catalogue.

The integration of multiple sources also introduces a critical challenge: the need for consistent and unambiguous identifiers. When different platforms describe the same software packages, researchers, or organizations, discrepancies in naming conventions, metadata formats, and identifier systems can arise. This issue underscores the importance of establishing a robust framework for identifier management.

As we move forward, the next section will delve into the role of identifiers in research software catalogues. By examining how persistent and unique identifiers can bridge the gaps between disparate sources, we aim to develop strategies that enhance interoperability, reduce ambiguity, and ultimately improve the discoverability and reusability of research software.

4.5 Research object identifiers

The next section will delve into the role of identifiers in research software catalogues. By examining how persistent and unique identifiers can bridge the gaps between disparate sources, we aim to develop strategies that enhance interoperability, reduce ambiguity, and ultimately improve the discoverability and reusability of research software.

Software identification

The primary focus of this catalogue is software packages. As such, the first step is to establish a robust method for software package identification. There is no single, universal approach; rather, several strategies have been developed over time.

Historically, a simple name or acronym was often sufficient for identification. However, as the number and diversity of software packages have grown, relying solely on a name has proven to be neither reliable nor precise. Consequently, additional identifiers have been introduced to enhance accuracy and ensure unambiguous reference.

In the course of our analysis, we identified several types of software package identifiers:

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Code source forge link

A source forge (or code forge) refers to a platform or website dedicated to hosting and managing open-source software projects. The most prominent example is SourceForge⁷⁶, one of the earliest and most well-known repositories for open-source software development and distribution. In recent years, platforms such as GitHub and *GitLab* have largely superseded *SourceForge*.

A source forge provides essential tools for software development, including code repository hosting, version control systems, collaboration features and software package distribution mechanisms.

For these reasons, research developers frequently share links to their source forge projects or repositories, as these links serve as direct pointers to their codebase, version history, commit logs, and other valuable metadata.

While linking to a source forge project may initially appear to be a robust method of identification, experience has shown that the longevity of such platforms can be unpredictable. The continued existence of a code hosting platform is often contingent upon the economic health and strategic priorities of the organisation managing the service. For instance, *Google Code*⁷⁷, an open-source code hosting platform operated by *Google*⁷⁸, was discontinued after just over five years of operation. This highlights the risk of broken links in academic publications and other references, underscoring the need for more persistent and reliable identification methods.

DOI

A **Digital Object Identifier (DOI)** is a standardized alphanumeric code used to uniquely identify an object – whether physical, digital, or abstract – and to ensure its persistent accessibility. Functionally, a DOI serves as a permanent link to an object's metadata and location, addressing the problem of maintaining reliable references to resources that may change over time. Structurally, a DOI consists of two components: a **prefix** that identifies the registrant (such as a publisher or institution) and a **suffix** that distinguishes the specific object, separated by a forward slash (e.g., *10.1000/182*). When formatted as a URL (e.g., <https://doi.org/10.1000/182>), it becomes a resolvable web address that redirects users to the current location of the resource.

DOIs are most commonly used for scholarly publications, datasets, software packages and other research outputs to provide persistent and reliable access. Each

⁷⁶ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q165400>

⁷⁷ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q10507565>

⁷⁸ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q95>

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DOI is registered with metadata containing bibliographic details (e.g., title, author, publisher, and publication date), which facilitates accurate discovery and management of digital resources in academic and professional contexts.

Governed by the **DOI Foundation**⁷⁹, the DOI system forms part of a broader digital infrastructure that supports the long-term accessibility and interoperability of scholarly content. It is widely adopted by publishers, repositories, and data archives, integrating with services such as CrossRef⁸⁰ and *DataCite*.

The DOI serves as an effective persistent identifier for citing software. However, its value is fully realized only when researchers who deposit records provide thorough and meaningful metadata; without such details, the identifier offers only limited information.

Software heritage identifier

A Software Heritage Identifier⁸¹ (SWHID) [12] is a unique and persistent identifier assigned to software artifacts—including source code, directories, releases, and snapshots—archived within the Software Heritage project. The SWHID is designed to ensure persistence, uniqueness, and verifiability, thereby facilitating the citation, referencing, and long-term preservation of software in academic, legal, and archival contexts.

While the *SWHID* is a relatively recent initiative, its adoption is steadily growing as awareness of its benefits spreads. Recognizing its value, we will harvest and record these identifiers in our catalogue, as they are increasingly integrated with established platforms such as *Zenodo*, *HAL*, and code-hosting services like *GitHub*, which now provide *SWHIDs* for repositories. This expanding integration highlights the identifier's growing relevance and utility in the scholarly and technical communities.

Others

Some catalogue instances, such as *bio.tools* and other domain-specific registries, maintain their own identification systems. These identifiers are both usable and relevant within their respective contexts. However, their primary limitation lies in their dependence on the long-term sustainability of the hosting catalogue. The notable advantage of such systems is their ability to address the specific needs of the scientific domain—for instance, by employing appropriate ontologies to accurately describe the functionalities of a software tool.

⁷⁹ <https://ror.org/01fyxcz70>

⁸⁰ <https://ror.org/02twcfp32>

⁸¹ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P6138>

Research identifiers

In the process of harvesting data about research software packages, we collect information not only on code but also on associated documents, individuals, organizations, and other relevant entities. For the same reasons that apply to software packages, it is essential to understand and navigate the various research identification systems in order to enrich the information available to users of our catalogue.

This section focuses on the principal identifiers for documents, organizations, and researchers.

ORCID, an identifier for persons

ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) is a unique, permanent identifier with international reach. Its purpose is to identify researchers unambiguously and unequivocally. ORCID makes it possible to reference all of a researcher's scientific output (articles, datasets, code) and career details (biography, employment, education, professional activities, European research projects, etc.). Most international publishers and funding agencies require researchers to use an ORCID. ORCID is the most widely used persistent identifier for researchers internationally. The ORCID non-profit organisation is supported by 1,493 member organisations (including the consortium) at the time of writing.

Composed of four sequences of four digits, the presence of an ORCID ID in information systems facilitates the exchange of information (in accordance with FAIR principles). Today, this identifier allows users to connect to numerous academic platforms (HAL, Nakala⁸², Web of Science⁸³) and, if the author so chooses (by configuring their account), they can push notifications of their scientific work hosted on a national open archive to their ORCID (trusted third party system). The advantage of this setting is that it avoids the need to re-enter metadata and increases the visibility of the contributor's scientific output. ORCID's interoperability with different information systems (universities, funders, publishers) is a strong point at different stages of the research life cycle, such as article submission.

DOI – An Object Identifier

As previously noted, a DOI is not exclusive to software packages; it is assigned to a wide array of research outputs, including datasets, documentation, articles, reports, and other digital resources. This versatility makes the DOI an indispensable tool for linking and referencing the diverse components of scholarly work. A software package, for example, may have associated DOIs for its documentation, related

⁸² <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q125661749>

⁸³ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q1201886>

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datasets, or publications. This interconnected use of DOIs enhances citation accuracy, discovery, and the tracking of research outputs throughout their lifecycle.

The DOI system is widely recognized for its reliability and resilience. Once assigned, a DOI remains stable even if the object's location or hosting platform changes, as it always resolves to the resource's current location. This persistence is essential for preserving the integrity of scholarly references and ensuring the long-term accessibility of research outputs. For this reason, whenever possible, the catalogue prioritises saving DOIs during metadata harvesting.

ROR an identifier for research organisations

Created in 2019, the Research Organisation Registry⁸⁴ (ROR) is an international directory responsible for listing all research organisations and assigning them a unique, open and persistent identifier. Composed of nine alphanumeric characters and presented in the form of a URI, the ROR ID⁸⁵ is readable by both machines and humans. The presence of the ROR in various information systems (HAL, OpenAlex⁸⁶, Zenodo, CrossRef, DataCite, etc.) promotes interoperability between them.

ROR is operated as a collaborative initiative⁸⁷ by the California Digital Library⁸⁷, *Crossref*, and *DataCite*. There are no fees to access and use ROR. ROR data are freely and openly available without any restrictions under the Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain dedication. ROR code is openly available on GitHub under a MIT Licence.

The primary objective of the Research Organizations Registry is therefore to uniquely identify research-related institutions (universities, research centres and laboratories, hospitals, companies, etc.). The ROR also serves to link researchers (via ORCID) to the research institutions to which they belong. As a result, researchers' scientific output can be easily identified and promoted.

Today, its international reputation is based on:

- the number of contributors who continuously enrich it (more than 107,000 entries recorded in 2024)
- the use of open standards and formats for data

⁸⁴ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q110235640>

⁸⁵ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q63565260> & <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P6782>

⁸⁶ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q107507571>

⁸⁷ <https://ror.org/03yrm5c26>

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- the possibility of linking structures (child organisations / parent organisations / related organisations / predecessor organisations)
- querying the registry via an API request
- the attribution of Creative Commons licences for data,
- the implementation of a moderation process with compliance checks against the required criteria (presence of identifiers from national registers : ISNI for the United Kingdom, RingoIID for the United States, RNSR for France, presence of scientific output (DOI) allowing affiliation to be verified, etc.).

Exemple : University Grenoble Alpes: <https://ror.org/02rx3b187>

More identifiers to add

We will incorporate the identifiers previously discussed, as they contribute to the accuracy and longevity of our data. However, we recognise that other identifier registries exist, and their inclusion is necessary to ensure broader compatibility. It is important, though, to proceed with caution: supporting an excessive number of registries could introduce unnecessary complexity and significantly increase maintenance efforts.

Source for linking identifiers

The importance of platforms such as Wikidata, which facilitate the linking of identifiers across databases, is noteworthy. For instance, within this database, one can observe the connections between a website URL, a Research Organization Registry (ROR) identifier, and a country-specific identifier.

5. Software Catalogue Application Architecture

In previous sections, we identified the requirements and challenges involved in creating a software catalogue that meets the needs of the scientific communities. We summarized the key elements: data model, data sources, use cases, and critical data points. This section shifts focus to the technical aspects, exploring the technologies, design patterns, key components, and best practices that will address these challenges.

5.1 Global architecture

When designing a web application, selecting the right software architecture is crucial, as each pattern offers unique benefits and trade-offs. The choice of architecture impacts not only the development process but also the application's scalability, maintainability, and performance. Below, we explore four prominent architectural patterns, detailing their characteristics, advantages, and potential drawbacks.

General concepts

Monolithic

In a monolithic architecture, all components of the application—including the user interface (frontend), business logic (backend), and data storage (database)—are tightly integrated into a single, unified codebase. This approach simplifies development and deployment, as everything is contained within one project, making it easier to manage dependencies and ensure consistency across the application.

However, as the application grows in size and complexity, a monolithic architecture can become cumbersome. Scaling specific parts of the application independently is challenging, and even small changes may require redeploying the entire system. This can lead to longer development cycles and increased risk of introducing errors during updates.

Client-Server

The client-server model separates the application into two distinct layers: the client (frontend) and the server (backend). The client, typically a web browser or mobile application, is responsible for presenting the user interface and handling user interactions. The server, on the other hand, manages business logic, data processing, and database operations. Communication between the client and server occurs through requests and responses, often using HTTP/HTTPS protocols.

This separation of concerns allows for clearer division of labour between frontend and backend developers. It also enables the server to be scaled independently of the client, which is particularly useful for applications with a large user base. However, the client-server model can introduce latency, as each interaction requires a round-trip between the client and server. Additionally, the backend can become a bottleneck if not properly optimised.

Microservices

Microservices architecture decomposes the application into a collection of small, loosely-coupled services, each responsible for a specific business function. These services operate independently, communicate with each other via well-defined APIs (often using REST⁸⁸ or messaging protocols), and can be developed, deployed, and scaled individually.

⁸⁸ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q749568>

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This approach offers significant advantages in terms of scalability and flexibility. Teams can work on different services simultaneously, using the most appropriate technologies for each task. Microservices also enable continuous delivery and deployment, as updates to one service do not require changes to others. However, the complexity of managing multiple services, ensuring consistent data across services, and handling inter-service communication can be substantial. Microservices architectures often require robust DevOps⁸⁹ practices and infrastructure to be effective.

Serverless

Serverless architecture shifts the responsibility of managing server infrastructure to third-party cloud providers. Developers focus solely on writing code in the form of functions, which are executed in response to specific events or triggers. The cloud provider automatically handles scaling, load balancing, and server management, allowing developers to concentrate on application logic.

This model is particularly well-suited for applications with variable or unpredictable workloads, as it can scale dynamically and users only pay for the compute resources they consume. Serverless architectures also reduce operational overhead, as there is no need to manage servers or infrastructure. However, potential drawbacks include vendor lock-in, as applications become dependent on the cloud provider's ecosystem, and challenges in debugging and monitoring distributed, event-driven functions.

LUMEN Constraints and Pattern Selection

The LUMEN project demands a modular and adaptable architecture. As the project evolves, new challenges will inevitably arise, necessitating a design that can accommodate change and integrate seamlessly with other LUMEN developments. To achieve this, the architecture should emphasize code modularity, reusability of existing community packages, and the use of independent scripts or jobs to enhance scalability and workload distribution.

The system must expose data to both a frontend application and other LUMEN services. The frontend will need to retrieve data from the database and also fetch information from additional LUMEN services.

Considering these requirements, the client-server pattern emerges as the most appropriate choice. A modern single-page frontend application⁹⁰ will interact with our

⁸⁹ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q3025536>

⁹⁰ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q1990286>

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API and, when necessary, directly request data from other LUMEN services. This approach balances flexibility, scalability, and integration needs.

5.2 Database & Software data

Software Metadata

As we mentioned before, all the sources from which we would like to fetch data, don't provide software metadata in the same format. Actually, each of them is different and usually we need to make multiple requests to their API.

To make it easier, we defined a unique way to describe metadata of a software. Following the analysis we made in the previous part we decided to use *CodeMeta*. The objective is to shape the data as it enters our system and avoid dealing with more than one format of data as part of our business logic.

Other data related to a piece of software

While *CodeMeta* provides a robust standard for software metadata, its scope is limited to describing software itself. Notably, it does not address the broader context of code repositories, which are essential for comprehensive software documentation. To address this gap, we are extending *CodeMeta* by **developing an ontology specifically focused on code repository description**.

During the proof-of-concept phase, we encountered the need to systematically capture and store a variety of data associated with software packages. This included related publications, contributing authors, and associated websites, among other elements. Given that *CodeMeta* is built upon the *Schema.org* framework, we have chosen to leverage this same ontology to structure and describe these additional data points. This approach ensures consistency across our metadata standards and facilitates interoperability with existing systems.

Database

As the data that this app is processing is mainly JSONbased, it makes sense that we use modern database handling and specialise in having native JSON documents. There is a large range of specialised databases, each one providing different specific features.

The following is a list of the main specialised open source JSON document databases:

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Name	Main features	Licence
MongoDB ⁹¹	Document-oriented NoSQL database; supports sharding, replication, ACID transactions ⁹² (from v4.0); flexible schema; rich query language; managed cloud service (Atlas).	Server Side Public License (SSPL) for Community Edition (since 2018);
CouchDB ⁹³	Document-oriented NoSQL database; uses JSON for data storage; HTTP/JSON API; multi-master replication; offline-first capabilities; MapReduce views.	Apache License 2.0
PostgreSQL ⁹⁴	Object-relational database; supports SQL ⁹⁵ (with extensions); ACID compliance; advanced indexing; JSON/JSONB support; extensible; synchronous and asynchronous replication.	PostgreSQL License (permissive, BSD/MIT-like)
MySQL ⁹⁶	Relational database; supports SQL; high performance; replication; clustering; dual licensing model. Community Edition is fully functional.	GNU General Public License (GPL) v2 for Community Edition.
OrientDB ⁹⁷	Multi-model (graph, document, key-value, object), SQL-like query language, ACID transactions, distributed architecture	Apache License 2.0 for Community Edition.

At the current stage of the project, and given the time available for the proof of concept, it remains challenging to definitively assess the long-term requirements for our software catalogue. Initially, *PostgreSQL* and *MySQL* appear to meet our basic needs effectively, providing sufficient functionality for the use cases we have encountered so far.

However, as the volume of documents and data complexity increases, databases such as *MongoDB*, *CouchDB*, and *OrientDB* may offer greater efficiency and scalability. These systems are specifically designed to handle large-scale,

⁹¹ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q1165204>

⁹² <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q288435>

⁹³ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q1136882>

⁹⁴ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q192490>

⁹⁵ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q47607>

⁹⁶ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q850>

⁹⁷ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q808716>

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unstructured, or semi-structured data, which could become a critical advantage in future phases of the project.

During our experimentation, we utilised the SIL platform, which relies on *PostgreSQL*. This solution has proven capable of supporting the core features required by our application, including the storage of JSON data within fields and the execution of basic queries. At present, there is no compelling reason to transition to an alternative database system. Nevertheless, once we begin to undertake massive data imports (such as those from extensive repositories like Zenodo) it will be prudent to reassess our technical needs and evaluate whether our current infrastructure remains optimal or if a more scalable solution should be adopted.

5.3 Backend : API and automated data collection

Programming Language

Given our commitment to an open design architecture, our system could theoretically accommodate multiple programming languages within the code stack. However, to ensure consistency, maintainability, and ease of collaboration, we have decided to limit the use of additional languages to only those scenarios where a specific technical requirement cannot be met by our chosen primary language.

We reduce our choice to two languages that have both interesting strengths for our project: python and javascript. In this section, we analyze these two languages to determine the most suitable primary language for our project.

Python

Python⁹⁸ is renowned for its readability and ease of use, making it an excellent choice for both beginners and experienced developers. Its simple, clean syntax allows for rapid development and prototyping, which is particularly advantageous in research and development environments.

The Python ecosystem is supported by a vast array of packages available through pip, the Python Package Index⁹⁹ (PyPI). Notably, Python is widely adopted in the scientific and research communities. Additionally, Python offers robust web frameworks such as Django¹⁰⁰ and Flask¹⁰¹, which are well-suited for building scalable and maintainable APIs.

⁹⁸ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q28865>

⁹⁹ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q2984686>

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q842014>

¹⁰¹ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q289281>

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Advantages:

- Rapid development and prototyping
- Extensive libraries for research and scientific applications
- Strong community support and documentation

Limitations:

- Performance may be a concern for CPU-intensive tasks
- Global Interpreter Lock (GIL) can limit multi-threading capabilities

JavaScript with Node.js

JavaScript¹⁰² was originally designed as a client-side scripting language for web browsers. However, the introduction of Node.js¹⁰³ has enabled its use for server-side development, making JavaScript a full-stack language. Node.js is built on Chrome¹⁰⁴'s V8 JavaScript engine, which provides high performance and efficiency for backend applications.

Node.js benefits from a rich ecosystem of packages available through the npm (Node Package Manager¹⁰⁵) registry, one of the largest package repositories in the world. This ecosystem includes a wide range of tools and libraries for web development, data processing, and integration with research repositories and source code management systems.

Advantages:

- Full-stack capability, allowing for code reuse between frontend and backend
- Non-blocking, event-driven architecture for high performance in I/O-bound applications
- Extensive package ecosystem and active community
- Already made open source software catalogue to rely on or pick components

Limitations:

- JavaScript's dynamic typing can lead to maintainability challenges in large codebases
- Single-threaded nature may require additional effort for CPU-intensive tasks

¹⁰² <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q2063>

¹⁰³ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q756100>

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q777>

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q7067518>

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Choice

Several programming languages could be effectively employed for the development of our application. However, a deliberate and informed choice is necessary to ensure optimal outcomes.

Both *Python* and *JavaScript* present compelling advantages, particularly due to their extensive ecosystems of packages. These ecosystems not only facilitate accelerated development by leveraging pre-existing libraries but also enable contributions to the community by addressing identified issues or gaps in functionality. Thus, either language could serve as a viable option for our project.

Given our decision to implement a single-page application (SPA) architecture for the frontend, JavaScript emerges as the natural choice. JavaScript frameworks are specifically designed to support SPAs, offering robust tools for dynamic and responsive user interfaces. Furthermore, adopting a unified language for both frontend and backend development simplifies code maintenance and promotes seamless code sharing between the two layers.

For these reasons, we have elected to utilise JavaScript for the backend, leveraging the Node.js runtime environment to execute server-side logic efficiently. This approach ensures consistency, streamlines development, and maximises the potential for code reuse across the application stack.

Ports & Adapters Architecture

In this project, we decided to use the *Ports & Adapters Architecture*¹⁰⁶ (also known as Hexagonal Architecture) to ensure a clean separation between the core business logic and the external systems or frameworks. This approach allows the application's domain layer to remain independent of technical details such as databases, user interfaces, or third-party services. By isolating the business logic, we can focus on implementing and testing the core features without being distracted by infrastructure concerns, leading to a more maintainable and robust codebase.

Another key reason for adopting this architecture is its flexibility. Ports & Adapters make it easy to swap out external components—such as databases, APIs, or even user interfaces—without affecting the core logic. For example, if we need to switch from a relational database to a *NoSQL* solution, or from a *REST API* to a *GraphQL*¹⁰⁷ endpoint, we only need to update the corresponding adapter, not the business logic.

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q66403655>

¹⁰⁷ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q25104949>

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This adaptability is especially valuable in fast-moving projects where requirements or technologies may evolve over time.

Finally, the *Ports & Adapters Architecture* significantly improves testability. Since the core logic is decoupled from external dependencies, we can write unit and integration tests using mock implementations of the ports. This makes it easier to achieve high test coverage and ensures that the business logic is thoroughly validated, even before the actual external systems are integrated. Overall, this architecture helps us build a scalable, maintainable, and future-proof application.

SourceGateway: an adapter interface component to source

The **SourceGateway** is a component responsible for handling data requests from an API. Since each source has its own format and network protocols, a unique adapter is needed for each one. To ensure interoperability, all adapters produce a standardized output: a **CodeMeta document**. This standardization also allows the adapters to be reused across different contexts, such as scripting, parsing, or analysis. We plan to implement adapters for the sources we previously selected: *Zenodo*, *HAL*, *SWH*, *GitLab*, and *GitHub*.

In the following, we defined the main components of the Adapter that allow us to handle source-specific formats and requirements while maintaining consistent output for downstream use in our software catalogue application.

The *SourceGateway* component has been designed to provide a standardised interface, enabling its use independently of the underlying data source API. This abstraction is achieved through the implementation of several key methods, which facilitate consistent interaction with software package data.

- Retrieve All Software Packages : Fetches a comprehensive list of all available software packages.
- Retrieve a Single Software Package : Retrieves detailed information for a specific software package by identifier.
- Search Software Packages by Name : Searches for software packages based on a provided name or partial name.

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Software Metadata Updater

The **Software Metadata Updater** is a dedicated component designed to ensure that software metadata remains current and consistent across all integrated sources. Its primary function is to systematically retrieve, process, and update information for software entries already registered in the system.

Core Functionality

- **Data Retrieval:** The updater fetches previously saved software entries, along with their unique identifiers, from each connected source.
- **Source Integration:** It then queries these sources to collect the latest available software metadata.
- **Database Synchronization:** The retrieved information is then used to update and refresh the local CodeMeta-formatted database, maintaining the accuracy and relevance of all registered software entries.

Technical Implementation The updater leverages a modular **interface layer**, referred to as an *adapter* or *SourceGateway*, which standardizes communication with diverse data sources. This abstraction ensures flexible integration and scalability, allowing seamless integration with new or existing platforms.

Operational Workflow To maintain up-to-date records, the updater is embedded within an automated script that runs as an **automated scheduled task**. This script is

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scheduled to run nightly, providing daily updates and ensuring that users always access the most current and reliable software metadata available.

Automated Source Discovery and Linking

When a software package is registered in our system, it frequently includes identifiers referencing other external sources—such as repositories, registries, or platforms—that may contain additional relevant data. For instance, a package recorded on *Zenodo* might provide a link to its corresponding *GitLab* repository. To leverage this interconnected data ecosystem, we aim to implement tools capable of automatically discovering these new sources and importing the associated data without manual intervention.

The core component responsible for this process operates either on demand or at scheduled intervals, depending on the frequency required for updating external data. Initially, the component retrieves from the database all available software package identifiers and their associated metadata. It then cross-references this list against our registry of recognized sources to identify matches.

For each identified match, the relevant software identifier is recorded in our database, effectively integrating it into the set of packages for which we actively collect information. The imported data are standardised and stored in the CodeMeta format, ensuring consistency and facilitating subsequent processing or merging by other system components.

However, it is not uncommon to encounter software packages or resource document identifiers that, while well-referenced, cannot be accessed due to the absence of an appropriate *SourceGateway* or the necessary credentials. Addressing these limitations will be essential to maximizing the completeness and reliability of our metadata collection process.

Database Connector

This component serves as the interface between our application and the database, abstracting the underlying structure, complexity, and specific database technology in use. By encapsulating all database interactions within this dedicated layer, we ensure that any future transition to a different database system will only require the development of a new connector, rather than a complete redesign of the core application. This approach significantly enhances the modularity and maintainability of the application, allowing for greater flexibility and scalability as requirements evolve.

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Metadata Validation

To guarantee the quality and reliability of our imported software packages, we implement a specialised validation component. This component will be responsible for automatically rejecting any software package during the import process if its metadata fails to meet the defined quality standards.

The component is designed to be highly flexible, recognizing that different sources - such as *GitHub* or *Zenodo* - provide varying sets of metadata. As such, it will not enforce a one-size-fits-all approach; instead, it will allow for source-specific validation rules, ensuring that only the relevant mandatory fields are required for each source.

When processing a software item, the component will take as input the item's metadata, formatted according to the *CodeMeta* schema, along with a set of filtering options. These options will specify which fields are mandatory, the expected data type for each field, and, where necessary, the allowed values or ranges. By enforcing these rules, the component will help maintain the integrity and consistency of our metadata, ensuring that only complete and valid information is accepted into our system.

Data Merging and Priority Handling

A critical component of the backend is the merge function, which consolidates multiple *CodeMeta*-formatted documents into a single, unified output. This function not only merges the data but also preserves the origin of each data point, ensuring that the highest-priority source is always retained during the merge process.

Merge Logic and Priority Rules

- **Priority-Based Merging:** The component merges documents field by field, attributing the priority level according to the priority level of the source where it was collected. If a field is missing in the highest-priority document, the function falls back to the next document in the priority order. So far we value research source as priority then repository source as complementary source. We will look for software package metadata source quality analysis to rank further sources.
- **Origin Tracking:** The function records the source of each data point, allowing for full traceability of where each piece of information originated.

Output Modes

The merge function supports two distinct output modes:

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- Standard Mode: Presents only the merged data, without additional metadata.
- Detailed Mode: Includes both the merged data and metadata about the source(s) of each field, as well as any discrepancies between sources.

Future Enhancements

In the long term, the system component could be extended to allow customizable priority rules for merging. This would enable users to set priority of a source at the metadata field level (e.g., *HAL* has a higher priority for "scientific domain" field than *GitHub*, but *GitHub* has a higher priority for "software version" field than *HAL*).

5.4 Frontend, user interface (UI) and user experience (UX)

Why do we use single page applications ?

The evolution of web development paradigms has led to the widespread adoption of *Single Page Applications* (SPAs) as the preferred architectural approach for modern, interactive web interfaces. This shift is primarily driven by the inherent advantages that SPAs offer over traditional websites using Multi-Page Applications (MPAs), as well as broader technological and user experience trends.

Architecturally, SPAs operate by dynamically rewriting the current page with new data from the server, rather than loading entire new pages. This approach eliminates full-page reloads, resulting in significantly faster navigation and a more fluid user experience akin to native applications. In contrast, MPAs rely on server-rendered pages, which necessitate full page refreshes and are consequently more susceptible to latency and perceived sluggishness.

Performance-wise, SPAs demonstrate superior efficiency following the initial load, as subsequent interactions require only incremental data transfers. This reduction in server requests and bandwidth usage is particularly advantageous in environments with constrained connectivity. However, the initial load time of SPAs can be longer due to the need to download comprehensive JavaScript bundles and assets—a trade-off that modern optimization techniques (e.g., code splitting, lazy loading) seek to mitigate.

From a development perspective, SPAs benefit from the modular, component-based paradigms introduced by contemporary JavaScript frameworks such as React¹⁰⁸, Angular¹⁰⁹, and Vue¹¹⁰. These frameworks facilitate the creation of reusable,

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q19399674>

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q28925578>

¹¹⁰ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q24589705>

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maintainable codebases and support advanced state management solutions, thereby enhancing developer productivity and reducing time-to-market. The decoupling of frontend and backend systems, enabled by RESTful APIs and GraphQL, further promotes scalability and independent evolution of application layers.

The rise of SPAs is also closely linked to the proliferation of mobile devices and the expectation for web applications to deliver app-like experiences. The ability to function offline, support push notifications, and be installed as Progressive Web Apps¹¹¹ (PWAs) has solidified SPAs as a versatile solution for cross-platform deployment. Additionally, the robust ecosystem surrounding SPAs—comprising extensive libraries, development tools, and community support—has lowered the barrier to entry and accelerated innovation.

Notwithstanding these advantages, SPAs are not without limitations. Historically, search engine optimization¹¹² (SEO) posed a challenge due to the reliance on client-side rendering, though solutions such as server-side rendering and static site generation have largely addressed this concern. Security considerations, particularly the risk of cross-site scripting attacks, also necessitate rigorous validation and sanitization practices.

In summary, the ascendancy of SPAs in recent years can be attributed to their alignment with the demands of modern web users—namely, speed, interactivity, and seamless cross-device functionality—as well as the technological advancements that have made their development and deployment increasingly feasible. While MPAs remain relevant for content-centric, SEO-critical applications, the trend towards SPAs reflects a broader industry shift towards dynamic, user-centric web experiences.

Which framework to use for SPAs ?

The selection of a *JavaScript* framework for *Single Page Application* (SPA) development plays a critical role in shaping not only the development workflow but also the performance, scalability, and long-term maintainability of the final product. While leading frameworks, *React*, *Angular*, and *Vue*, each present unique strengths and trade-offs, the specific requirements of the software catalogue project do not necessitate the adoption of a particular framework due to feature limitations or technical constraints.

¹¹¹ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q23679990>

¹¹² <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q180711>

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Given that this software component is integrated within the broader *LUMEN project* ecosystem, where *React* is already the established standard, the decision to align with existing infrastructure and tooling is both pragmatic and strategic. This approach ensures consistency, leverages shared resources, and facilitates seamless collaboration across teams.

UI/UX concept for the catalogue

At this stage, the *LUMEN project* is still in its early phases of development, and as such, it is not yet mature enough to propose overall *User Interface*¹¹³ and *User Experience*¹¹⁴ (UI/UX) concept and visual mockups for the software catalogue. But as we already assess basic needs for data visualisation and gathered user needs we can already propose some concepts .

Given the project's current priorities, there is no immediate necessity to invest resources in defining theme colours, logos, or the general high-level organization of the user interface. These aspects, while important for the final product, are secondary to ensuring that the catalogue's foundational components are functional, intuitive, and aligned with user workflows.

However, the use cases previously defined provide a solid foundation for detailing specific UI components and their expected behaviours. By concentrating on these elements, the team can ensure that the catalogue's interface is both practical and user-centric, even at this early stage.

Search component

A robust search feature is essential for users navigating software catalogue. It should be intuitive, allowing for both quick overviews and detailed filtering to meet diverse user needs presented in Section 3.

At the heart of the search experience is a simple text box, where users can enter queries. The system analyses this input to find matches across multiple fields, including:

- Software names
- Keywords
- Software descriptions
- Software categories
- Research fields

¹¹³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/User_interface

¹¹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/User_experience

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- Authors or developers
- Organisations linked to the software teams or authors

Once initial results are displayed, users need the ability to refine their search using a dedicated filter panel. Key filter options include:

- Field of research
- Year
- Operating system
- Features
- Licence
- Programming language

To further enhance usability, results can be ordered by:

- Last update (release of a software package) (most recent first by default)
- Last change or sign of “life” (commit) (most recent first by default)
- Most citations (most cited first by default)

By combining a straightforward search interface with powerful filtering and sorting capabilities, users can efficiently locate the most relevant software for their needs.

Understanding Software Package Maturity and Lifespan

Users need immediate insight into a project’s development status and code maturity. To meet this need, we focus on a curated set of metrics that paint a comprehensive picture:

- **Commit Activity** tracks the number of commits over time, whether daily, weekly, monthly, or yearly, revealing the rhythm and intensity of development efforts.
- **Issue Resolution** measures the number of issues opened versus closed, along with the average resolution time, offering a window into the project’s responsiveness and efficiency.
- **Release Frequency** highlights the number and regularity of releases—major, minor, and patch—indicating the project’s commitment to continuous improvement and stability.
- **Community Health** is reflected in the number of forks, stars, pull requests, and community discussions, showcasing the project’s reach, engagement, and collaborative spirit.

A Unified Visualization Component

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To make this wealth of information accessible at a glance, we propose a unified dashboard component. This all-in-one view would feature:

- A **timeline** that maps out commits and releases over the years, providing a historical perspective on development milestones.
- A **dedicated section** for issue tracking, displaying the number of open and closed issues alongside the average resolution time, all in a single, cohesive line.
- A **community metrics bar** that presents the number of contributors, forks, and stars or followers, offering a snapshot of the project's popularity and collaborative energy.

By integrating these elements into a single, intuitive interface, users can effortlessly assess the vitality and trajectory of a software project.

Keywords: organised and Colour-Coded

Keywords serve as quick reference points, guiding users to relevant features or research areas. To maximise clarity, we recommend displaying each keyword within a **rounded rectangular box**, clearly separated from others. A **colour-coded system** further enhances readability:

- **colour 1**: for feature-related keywords, making it easy to spot functionality at a glance.
- **colour2**: for research subtypes, helping users identify academic or specialized applications.

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While picking colour, keep in mind to use a high contrast colour distinction in line with accessibility regulations to ensure readability for all users. This approach not only organises information but also creates a visual hierarchy, allowing users to scan and filter content efficiently.

Operating System Compatibility: Instant Recognition

Compatibility with different operating systems is a critical factor for users. Instead of text lists, we use the **official logos** of supported operating systems (e.g., Windows¹¹⁵, macOS¹¹⁶, Linux¹¹⁷, Android¹¹⁸). Logos are universally recognised and instantly convey compatibility, reducing cognitive load and improving user experience.

External Sources and References: Accessible and Trustworthy

External sources and references add credibility and depth to documentation. To make them user-friendly:

- Present them as **clickable icons or logos** (e.g., *DOI*, *arXiv*, *GitHub*, or publisher logos).
- Ensure links open in a new tab, keeping the user's context intact.

¹¹⁵ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q1406>

¹¹⁶ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q14116>

¹¹⁷ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q388>

¹¹⁸ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q94>

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This method not only streamlines access to additional resources but also reinforces trust in the information provided.

Mentions: Contextualising Document Relevance

Understanding how often a software package is mentioned across different categories can indicate its popularity and applicability. To visualise this:

- Display the **category of the document** prominently.
- In the top-right corner, show the **number of documents mentioning the software per category** as a small, unobtrusive badge or counter.

This subtle yet effective design choice helps users gauge the software's relevance and adoption within specific fields.

As previously discussed regarding software package identifiers, there is currently no standardised identifier that is widely shared and adopted across communities. While obtaining data citations for software packages may present certain challenges, we wish to clarify that our catalogue will not directly implement such a system. Instead, we intend to rely on several ongoing initiatives in this area—such as *OpenAlex*, *Software Heritage*, and *SoFair*¹¹⁹—which are expected to provide data on software mentions and citations. Additionally, we may utilise a key publication associated with a software package and analyse the citations of that publication as a proxy for the software package itself.

Programming Languages: Visualising Code Accessibility

Software projects often utilise multiple programming languages, each contributing to different aspects of the codebase. To help users quickly assess code accessibility and language distribution:

- Use a **horizontal bar chart** to represent each programming language.
- The length of each bar corresponds to the **percentage of the codebase** written in that language.

This visualisation provides an immediate sense of the project's technical landscape, enabling developers to evaluate how easily they can contribute or integrate the software into their workflows.

¹¹⁹ <https://sofair.org/about/>

6. Software Catalogue as a Data Product

6.1 Integration within the LUMEN Data Mesh Ecosystem

Research software represents a specific type of scholarly output that requires specialised metadata and dedicated treatment. To avoid duplication of efforts and ensure optimal integration within the *LUMEN federation*, the software catalogue developed under T6.5 is designed to serve as a canonical data source, exposing its content through the *LUMEN Data Mesh architecture* [17].

This ensures consistency, promotes interoperability, and demonstrates a real-world implementation of the *Data Mesh concept*¹²⁰ within a multi-disciplinary research infrastructure.

6.2 Data Product Definition

According to the *LUMEN Data Model* (Deliverable 4.2: Lumen Data Model), a Data Product is defined using the Data Product Ontology¹²¹ (DPROD), which is based on DCAT¹²² (Data Catalogue Vocabulary). The complete description of the DataProduct will be finalized at the end of 2026, but a few elements can already be defined. For the software catalogue Data Product, some metadata can be formally described; we propose the following description, which will be finalized by the end of 2026:

¹²⁰ <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q110726242>

¹²¹ <https://ekgf.github.io/dprod/>

¹²² <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q16892890>

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Identifier: dp-lumen-software

Name: LUMEN Research Software Catalogue

Domain: Cross-disciplinary (Mathematics, Earth Systems, Social Sciences and Humanities, Molecular Dynamics)

Description: A governed collection of enriched software metadata records aggregated from multiple external sources (e.g., GitHub, GitLab, Software Heritage, HAL, Zenodo, bio.tools, swMATH) and enhanced with harmonised licences, version information, programming language details, dependencies, and links to repositories, publications, and citation data.

Purpose: To expose curated software metadata that enables discovery, proper citation, and reuse of research software across scientific communities, supporting reproducibility and FAIR principles.

Data Product Components

Following the DPROD model, the software catalogue Data Product consists of several key components for which we can tentatively define some metadata. Note that these metadata and definitions will be finalised at the end of 2026, along with the Data Product and Data Contract specification.

Input Dataset (dprod:inputDataset)

Dataset ID: dataset-software-metadata

Description: Aggregated software metadata harvested from multiple sources, enriched with additional metadata through automated analysis and curation. The dataset contains structured information about research software including identification, authorship, licensing, technical characteristics, and relationships to publications and datasets.

Conforms To: CodeMeta (<https://codemeta.github.io/terms/>)

Source Provenance: Metadata are harvested from:

- Code repositories: *GitHub*, *GitLab*
- Research archives: *HAL*, *Zenodo*
- Archival services: *Software Heritage*
- Specialized registries: *bio.tools* (bioinformatics), *swMATH* (mathematics)

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6.3 Data Contract Specification

The Data Contract, following the Open Data Contract Standard (ODCS), formalises the governance, access rules, quality commitments, and sustainability model for the software catalogue Data Product. The Data Contract for the software catalogue will be also finalised at the end of 2026.

6.4 API Specification and Access Patterns

6.4.1. Retrieve a Software by its Stable ID

- **URL:** `/api/software/{id}`
- **Method:** GET
- **Description:** Returns the complete metadata of a software identified by its ID. ID could be internal or other external source id SWHID or DOI.

Parameters

Name	Type	Description	Required
<code>id</code>	String	Internal ID, SWHID or DOI	Yes

Response (200 OK)

```
{
  "@context": "CodeMeta",
  "id": "12345-abcde",
  "name": "Software Name",
  "description": "Detailed description of the software.",
  "author": {
    "@type": "Organization",
    "name": "Organization Name"
  },
  "datePublished": "2025-01-01",
  "softwareVersion": "1.0.0",
  "operatingSystem": ["Linux", "Windows"],
  "license": "https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT",
  "keywords": ["metadata", "analysis", "tool"],
  "discipline": ["Computer Science", "Data Science"],
  "codeRepository": "https://gitlab.com/example/repo",
  "downloadUrl": "https://example.com/download",
}
```


Possible Errors

- **404 Not Found:** If the ID does not match any software.
- **500 Internal Server Error:** In case of a server error.

6.4.2. List Software with Filters

- **URL:** `/api/software/{id}`
- **Method:** GET
- **Description:** Returns a **minimal list** of software entries filtered by the specified criteria. Use the `id` from this response to fetch full metadata via the `/api/software/{id}` endpoint.

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Query Parameters

Name	Type	Description	Example Value
<code>applicationCategory</code>	String	Filter by discipline/community (e.g., "Computer Science", "Biology"). Uses <code>applicationCategory</code> from CodeMeta.	<code>applicationCategory=Computer Science</code>
<code>keyword</code>	String	Filter by keyword in the name, description, or tags.	<code>keyword=analysis</code>
<code>license</code>	String	Filter by SPDX license identifier (e.g., MIT, GPL-3.0-only).	<code>license=MIT</code>
<code>minDate</code>	Date	Filter software published after this date (format: YYYY-MM-DD).	<code>minDate=2024-01-01</code>
<code>maxDate</code>	Date	Filter software published before this date (format: YYYY-MM-DD).	<code>maxDate=2025-12-31</code>
<code>limit</code>	Integer	Limit the number of results returned (default: 20).	<code>limit=10</code>
<code>offset</code>	Integer	Offset for pagination (default: 0).	<code>offset=20</code>

Response (200 OK)

```
{
  "count": 2,
  "offset": 0,
  "limit": 10,
  "results": [
    {
      "id": "12345-abcde",
      "name": "Software A",
      "description": "Data analysis tool for research.",
      "applicationCategory": ["Computer Science", "Data Science"],
      "license": "MIT",
      "datePublished": "2024-10-15",
      "softwareVersion": "2.1.0"
    },
    {
      "id": "67890-fghij",
      "name": "Software B",
      "description": "Simulation software for biology.",
      "applicationCategory": ["Biology", "Computer Science"],
      "license": "GPL-3.0-only",
      "datePublished": "2024-09-01",
      "softwareVersion": "1.5.0"
    }
  ]
}
```

Possible Errors

- **400 Bad Request:** If a parameter is malformed (e.g., invalid date, negative `limit`, or invalid SPDX license).
- **404 Not Found:** If no results match the filters.
- **500 Internal Server Error:** In case of a server error.

6.5 Benefits, Challenges, and Sustainability Strategy

Expected Benefits

The integration of the software catalogue as a Data Product within the LUMEN federation offers significant advantages for both the project consortium and the wider research community.

First, the catalogue provides specialized metadata and presentation capabilities tailored to research software, including programming languages, dependencies, and version control information, along with visualization tools optimized for software discovery and reuse.

By establishing the catalogue as the canonical source for software metadata, WP4 (White Label Platform) benefits from reduced development effort and maintenance overhead, avoiding the need to implement its own software harvesting infrastructure. Rather than each LUMEN service developing separate harvesting mechanisms, the catalogue serves as a single, authoritative source that can be consumed by all federation components. This approach builds upon tools and services already developed for the national software catalogue initiative, while adapting them as a Data Product for LUMEN.

This design decision exemplifies effective cross-WP collaboration and provides a concrete, operational implementation of the Data Mesh concept within a real-world research infrastructure, through coordination between WP6 (Software Catalogue), WP4 (White Label Platform), WP3 (MetaSearch), and other LUMEN services.

Beyond the immediate technical benefits, this integration enhances the visibility and potential reuse of the Software Catalogue far beyond its original national scope. By exposing the catalogue through standardized APIs and data contracts, it becomes accessible not only to LUMEN services but also to external platforms and research communities. This provides a compelling demonstration of FAIR interoperability, showcasing how infrastructure components and content providers can work together seamlessly through well-defined interfaces and governance models.

Identified Challenges and Risks

While the integration strategy offers substantial benefits, it also introduces specific challenges that require careful management. The primary concern is the creation of a technical dependency between WP4 (Discovery Platform Building, particularly

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regarding the LUMEN data mesh framework) and the current task (WP6 on software catalogue development), which necessitates coordinated release cycles and ongoing schema alignment efforts. This coupling also means that changes to the catalogue's data model or API must be carefully planned and communicated to avoid disrupting consuming services.

An additional technical challenge concerns the classification and filtering of software entries by scientific discipline, which is not systematically provided by source repositories. A significant risk relates to the temporal mismatch between project work packages, creating potential challenges for technical support, bug fixes, and feature evolution during a critical integration period. Additionally, maintaining API stability and comprehensive documentation is essential to ensure smooth integration, but requires sustained effort and resources.

Risk Mitigation and Sustainability Strategy

To address these challenges, the strategy is the designation of at least one technical contact within WP6 who will remain responsible for catalogue maintenance and support throughout 2026, ensuring continuity all along the project.

Operationally, the mitigation plan includes the following key elements:

- Scheduled joint WP4–WP6 checkpoints: recurrent meetings to monitor integration progress, discuss schema evolution, and early identification of potential issues and collaborative problem-solving.
- Formal versioning and change control: define a process for the Software Catalogue API/Data Product.
- Project-level visibility: Explicit inclusion of the WP4–WP6 dependency in the joint technical roadmap, reviewed during Technical Committee meetings to ensure appropriate resource allocation and timeline coordination.
- Comprehensive documentation: Maintenance of OpenAPI specifications and user guides to facilitate knowledge transfer and ensure continued operation.

This approach balances the benefits of integration with the need for long-term stability and sustainability and combines technical best practices (versioning, documentation) with organizational mechanisms (dedicated contacts, regular checkpoints, oversight).

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To address the issues concerning discipline-based filtering, several approaches will be explored from text mining and keyword extraction to AI-powered text classification. Depending on the source to be harvested, it can also be possible to exploit existing classifications from the software repository sources.

7. Conclusion

This report presents the global architecture of the research software catalogue developed within Work Package 6 of the LUMEN project. This infrastructure aims to address a fundamental need of the scientific community: facilitating the discovery, citation, and reuse of research software in a multidisciplinary context.

The adopted approach relies on three main pillars. First, **metadata standardization** through the adoption of CodeMeta as the reference ontology, enabling harmonized software description regardless of the source of origin. Second, a **multi-source aggregation strategy** that combines metadata from code repositories (GitHub, GitLab), research archives (HAL, Zenodo), archival services (Software Heritage), and specialized registries (bio.tools, swMATH). Third, a **modular architecture** comprising data collectors, an entity matching system, a metadata enricher, and exploitation interfaces tailored to user needs.

The integration of the catalogue as a Data Product within the LUMEN federation constitutes a concrete demonstration of the Data Mesh concept and promotes interoperability between different Work Packages, notably with WP4 (White Label Platform) and WP3 (MetaSearch), while avoiding redundancy in software metadata collection and enrichment efforts.

Several **technical and organizational challenges** have been identified. The disciplinary classification of software, rarely provided by source repositories, requires the exploration of text analysis and automatic classification techniques. The temporal mismatch between Work Package schedules represents a risk for maintenance and technical support during the critical integration phase.

To mitigate these risks, a **sustainability strategy** has been defined, structured around the designation of dedicated technical contacts, regular synchronisation checkpoints between WP4 and WP6, and comprehensive documentation including API specifications. This governance combines technical best practices and organisational mechanisms to ensure long-term service stability.

Beyond its initial role within LUMEN, the software catalogue aspires to become a reference resource for the European and international scientific community. By exposing its data through standardized APIs and adhering to *FAIR* principles, it paves the way for synergies with other infrastructures and national or European initiatives, thus demonstrating the scalability and reusability potential of components developed within the project framework.

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Next steps will include the finalization of *Data Product* and *Data Contract* specifications for the software catalogue by the end of 2026, the development of access APIs, the implementation of disciplinary classification mechanisms, and the operational deployment of the software catalogue in coordination with other *LUMEN federation services*.

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8. Annexes

8.1 [CodeMeta.org](https://code.meta.org/) fields

Data included in CodeMeta terms from *schema.org* terms : Software Application

Field Name	Type	Description
name	Text	The name of the item (software, Organization)
description	Text	A description of the item.
applicationCategory	Text or URL	Type of software application, e.g. 'Game, Multimedia'.
author	Organization or Person	The author of this content or rating. Please note that author is special in that HTML 5 provides a special mechanism for indicating authorship via the rel tag. That is equivalent to this and may be used interchangeably.
codeRepository	URL	Link to the repository where the un-compiled, human readable code and related code is located (SVN, GitHub, CodePlex, institutional GitLab instance, etc.).
dateCreated	Date	The date on which the CreativeWork was created or the item was added to a DataFeed.
dateModified	Date	The date on which the CreativeWork was most recently modified or when the item's entry was modified within a DataFeed.
datePublished	Date	Date of first broadcast/publication.
identifier	PropertyValue or URL	The identifier property represents any kind of identifier for any kind of Thing, such as ISBNs, GTIN codes, UUIDs etc. Schema.org provides dedicated properties for representing many of these, either as textual strings or as URL (URI) links. See background notes for more details.
keywords	Text	Keywords or tags used to describe this content. Multiple entries in a keywords list are typically delimited by commas.

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license	CreativeWork or URL	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL.
operatingSystem	Text	Operating systems supported (Windows 7, OSX 10.6, Android 1.6).
programmingLanguage	ComputerLanguage or Text	The computer programming language.
provider	Organization or Person	The service provider, service operator, or service performer; the goods producer. Another party (a seller) may offer those services or goods on behalf of the provider. A provider may also serve as the seller. Supersedes carrier.
runtimePlatform	Text	Runtime platform or script interpreter dependencies (Example - Java v1, Python2.3, .Net Framework 3.0). Supersedes runtime.
url	URL	URL of the item.
softwareVersion	Text	Version of the software instance.
softwareHelp	CreativeWork	Software application help.
citation	CreativeWork or URL	A citation or reference to another creative work, such as another publication, web page, scholarly article, etc.
funder	Organization or Person	A person or organization that supports (sponsors) something through some kind of financial contribution.
isAccessibleForFree	Boolean	A flag to signal that the publication is accessible for free.
relatedLink	URL	A link related to this object, e.g. related web pages
sponsor	Organization or Person	A person or organization that supports a thing through a pledge, promise, or financial contribution. e.g. a sponsor of a Medical Study or a corporate sponsor of an event.
sameAs	URL	URL of a reference Web page that unambiguously indicates the item's identity. E.g. the URL of the item's Wikipedia page, Wikidata entry, or official website.
applicationSubCategory	Text or URL	Subcategory of the application, e.g. 'Arcade Game'.
contributor	Organization or Person	A secondary contributor to the CreativeWork or Event.
copyrightHolder	Organization or Person	The party holding the legal copyright to the CreativeWork.
copyrightYear	Number	The year during which the claimed copyright for the CreativeWork was first asserted.
downloadUrl	URL	If the file can be downloaded, URL to download the binary.
editor	Person	Specifies the Person who edited the CreativeWork.
encoding	MediaObject	A media object that encodes this CreativeWork. This property is a synonym for associatedMedia. Supersedes encodings.

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fileFormat	Text or URL	Media type, typically MIME format (see IANA site) of the content e.g. application/zip of a SoftwareApplication binary. In cases where a CreativeWork has several media type representations, 'encoding' can be used to indicate each MediaObject alongside particular fileFormat information. Unregistered or niche file formats can be indicated instead via the most appropriate URL, e.g. defining Web page or a Wikipedia entry.
fileSize	Text	Size of the application / package (e.g. 18MB). In the absence of a unit (MB, KB etc.), KB will be assumed.
hasPart	CreativeWork	Indicates a CreativeWork that is (in some sense) a part of this CreativeWork. Reverse property isPartOf
installUrl	URL	URL at which the app may be installed, if different from the URL of the item.
isPartOf	CreativeWork	Indicates a CreativeWork that this CreativeWork is (in some sense) part of. Reverse property hasPart
memoryRequirements	Text or URL	Minimum memory requirements.
permissions	Text	Permission(s) required to run the app (for example, a mobile app may require full internet access or may run only on wifi).
position	Integer or Text	The position of an item in a series or sequence of items. (While schema.org considers this a property of CreativeWork, it is also the way to indicate ordering in any list (e.g. the Authors list). By default arrays are unordered in JSON-LD
processorRequirements	Text	Processor architecture required to run the application (e.g. IA64).
producer	Organization or Person	The person or organization who produced the work (e.g. music album, movie, tv/radio series etc.).
publisher	Organization or Person	The publisher of the creative work.
releaseNotes	Text or URL	Description of what changed in this version.
review	Review	A review of the source code.
softwareRequirements	SoftwareSourceCode	Required software dependencies
storageRequirements	Text or URL	Storage requirements (free space required).
supportingData	DataFeed	Supporting data for a SoftwareApplication.
targetProduct	SoftwareApplication	Target Operating System / Product to which the code applies. If applied to several versions, just the product name can be used.
version	Number or Text	The version of the CreativeWork embodied by a specified resource.

Data included in CodeMeta and not present in *schema.org*

Field Name	Type	Description
------------	------	-------------

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contIntegration	URL	link to continuous integration service
buildInstructions	URL	link to installation instructions/documentation
continuousIntegration	URL	link to continuous integration service
developmentStatus	Text	Description of development status, e.g. Active, inactive, suspended. See repostatus.org
embargoDate	Date	Software may be embargoed from public access until a specified date (e.g. pending publication, 1 year from publication)
embargoEndDate	Date	Software may be embargoed from public access until a specified date (e.g. pending publication, 1 year from publication)
funding	Text	Funding source (e.g. specific grant)
hasSourceCode	SoftwareSourceCode	Link that states where the software code is for a given software. For example a software registry may indicate that one of its software entries hasSourceCode in a GitHub repository.
isSourceCodeOf	SoftwareApplication	Link that states where software application is built from a given source code. This is the reverse property of 'hasSourceCode'.
issueTracker	URL	link to software bug reporting or issue tracking system
maintainer	Person	Individual responsible for maintaining the software (usually includes an email contact address)
readme	URL	link to software Readme file
referencePublication	ScholarlyArticle	An academic publication related to the software.
softwareSuggestions	SoftwareSourceCode	Optional dependencies , e.g. for optional features, code development, etc.

Data added by Catalogi

Field Name	Field Name	Type	Description
Thing	image	ImageObject or URL	An image of the item. This can be a URL or a fully described ImageObject.

